

DISPENSARY CONTROL OF CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL DEFECTS IN THE MAXILLOFACIAL SYSTEM ARRANGE TO RECEIVE.

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Abstract. In this article, dispensary control of children with congenital defects in the maxillofacial system is described in the organization of the reception. Babies born with congenital defects in the area of the face and jaws should receive preventive and effective specialized complex treatment under the supervision of a local (city, district) pediatric dentist and be monitored until the age of 14-15.

Keywords: dentist, rehabilitation, diagnosis, inpatient, dispensary.

Аннотация. В данной статье описана организация диспансерного наблюдения за детьми с врожденными дефектами челюстно-лицевой системы. Дети, рожденные с врожденными дефектами в области лица и челюстей, должны получать профилактическое и эффективное специализированное комплексное лечение под наблюдением участкового (городского, районного) детского стоматолога и находиться под наблюдением до 14-15 лет.

Ключевые слова: стоматолог, реабилитация, диагностика, стационар, диспансер.

The birth of a child with a defect (especially in the area of the face and jaws) causes parents to fall into a state of confusion and depression. They ask the medical staff a series of questions. They are worried about the reason why a child is born with such a defect, who, when, and where to treat it. Naturally, experts can answer these questions. Questions arise from the moment the child is born, and answers should be received without delay. Parents who cannot reliably get positive answers to their questions sometimes give up their children due to birth defects and leave them in the maternity ward. Almost every day, 2-3 children are born with defects of the upper lip and palate in the delivery rooms of our republic. How to organize high-level specialist care for a baby born with a defect and his mother? To establish a systematic service in this direction, it is necessary to have a republic-wide center, its branches in regions and districts, or involve local children's dentists.

According to the order of the Minister of Health of Uzbekistan No. 118 dated March 16, 2004, the "Republic Scientific and Practical Center for the Treatment and

Rehabilitation of Congenital and Acquired Defects of the Face and Jaw of Children" was established under the First Tashkent State Medical Institute (now TTA).

Tasks performed in the CENTER:

- development of medical theory and practice issues related to congenital and acquired defects of the face-jaw area in children on a scientific basis;
- organization of organizational and therapeutic work in the field, highly qualified specialized medical assistance at the level of modern requirements and coordination within the territory of the Republic;
- development of medical theory and operational issues related to inflammatory diseases and injuries of the face and jaw in children on a scientific basis;
- organization and implementation of high-level medical consultation assistance to ambulatory patients sent by health departments and institutions and who applied at their own choice;
- Provide highly qualified specialized care in inpatient conditions to sick children who need medical assistance in the center's specialty;
- development of new, scientifically based, effective methods of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of congenital and acquired defects and their implementation in the practice of medical institutions of the Republic, development of programs for the development and improvement of specialized medical care, reduction of disability indicators;
- publication of stylistic manuals, articles, and theses (monographs) in the field, creation of inspection and treatment standards, and active participation in training and retraining of personnel in the specialty, improving their skills;
- participation in foreign grants and competitions aimed at developing specialized, highly qualified, medical care based on modern technologies.

Dispensary monitoring of children with congenital malformations of the maxillofacial system externalization

From the day of birth, a child with a congenital malformation of the maxillofacial system should be supervised by a residential pediatric dentist dispensary. The place of residence of children who are under dispensary supervision in local children's dental polyclinics (Republic, region) must also be registered with the dispensary. The tasks of center specialists and resident children's stomatologists are divided, and each step must be understandable to both parties. Patients with congenital malformations of the maxillofacial region at the department and department of pediatric dentistry of TTA are divided into 5 groups:

Only children with congenital upper lip defects are included **in the first group**. In children of this group, a cheiloplasty operation is performed in the first days of birth

following the instructions in the maternity hospital or specialized surgical departments if there are instructions.

The second group includes children with congenital defects of the soft and hard palate. Operations on the palate: performed from 8-10 months (soft palate) to 2-5 years (soft and hard palate), that is, until the formation of conscious speech. Early operations serve to form the speech correctly from the beginning. After the operation, children in this group will be guided by a speech therapist to practice speech development and proper formation. If the operation is delayed due to various reasons, for example, if it is performed after the eruption of the molar teeth (at 2.5-3 years old) in cases of soft and hard palate defects, children start speech therapy exercises before the operation and continue them after the operation. Orthodontic treatment is also given to children with signs of retardation of jaw bone growth.

The third group includes children with a unilateral (upper lip, alveolar septum, palate) crossing birth defect. Children included in this group will need step-by-step orthodontic treatment, surgical intervention, and speech therapy exercises. From the first days of life, the functioning of the respiratory and nutritional systems is disturbed. The treatment plan is drawn up jointly by the surgeon, dentist, and orthodontist. Today, in the treatment of unilateral crossing birth defects, at the Department of Pediatric Dentistry of TTA, performing plates are used to separate the oral and nasal cavities, to bring the jaws closer together, and this plate helps to breathe through the nose and express milk from the mother's breast. Initially, the child is prepared until he is 6-7 months old, and then cheiloplasty is performed. After cheiloplasty, a new performing plate is worn and replaced several times. Veloplasty surgery is performed when the child is 10-14 months old. From the age of 2 to 2.5 years, he conducts speech therapy exercises based on the program conducted before the operation. After the child's first teeth come out, uranoplasty is performed. The orthodontist regularly examines the child in the last period of the operation, during the period of tooth replacement and when the permanent teeth are coming out, they ensure their correct eruption and the upper jaw does not lag behind the lower jaw with the help of appliances. Orthodontic supervision lasts for 14-15 years.

The fourth group includes children with bilateral (upper lip, alveolar septum, and palate) crossing defects. The defects of children included in this group are clinically the most severe. Compared to children with unilateral crossing congenital malformations, the middle lobe (premaxilla) is in a different degree of forward (protrusion) position. For this reason, the orthodontist takes measures to prevent the premaxilla from protruding forward and to move it back as much as possible. To prevent the premaxilla from moving forward, a special performing plate is made for such children. In some children, a special band is worn to push the premaxilla back.

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Cheiloplasty is performed on one side in a 3-4-month-old child, on the other side after 2.5-3 months, and veloplasty in 10-14 months; At the age of 3-4, a uranoplasty operation is performed. The recovery of the orbicularis oculi exerts pressure on the premaxilla, causing it to be pushed back. Children in this group will be under the supervision of an orthodontist and a speech therapist for many years.

The fifth group includes children with defects of the upper lip and palate, as well as congenital diseases of the central nervous system (inability to make a sound, deafness, and Down). Usually, such patients are under the supervision of a specialized dispensary. The dentist's task is to prepare and send them to a surgical dental intervention promptly. Orthodontic treatment in the deeply damaged central nervous system is decided individually.

Today, the center uses the services of all departments of the 3rd clinic of the TTA Academy to fully fulfill its tasks. In addition to maxillofacial surgeons, the center includes a pediatrician, anesthesiologist-reanimatologist, dentist-therapist, orthopedist-orthodontist, otorhinolaryngologist, speech therapist, and other specialists who provide qualified assistance to the patients who apply.

Each specialist in the center is assigned several tasks.

Every child with a congenital defect of the upper lip and palate should be examined by a pediatric dentist during the first days of treatment.

References:

- Abakarov S.I. Modern designs of removable dental prostheses: Tutorial. allowance — M., 1994.
- Aslanov K.L. Complications in the use of bridge prostheses and measures to prevent them: Author. dis... cand. med. science — M., 1984.
- Bolshakov G.V. Odontopreparation. — Saratov, 1983.
- Bolshakov G.V. Preparation of teeth for filling and prosthetics. - M.: Medicine, 1983.
- Borovsky E.V., Leontyev V.K. Biology of the oral cavity. - M.: Medicine, 1991.
- Bushan M.G., Kalamkarov H.A. Complications during dental prosthetics and their prevention. - Chisinau, 1983.
- Gavrilov E.I. Theory and clinic of prosthetics with partial removable dentures. - M.: Medicine, 1973.
- Gavrilov E.I. Prosthesis and prosthetic bed. - M., 1979.
- Gavrilov E.I., Shcherbakov A.S. Orthopedic dentistry: Textbook - M.: Medicine, 1984.
- Goncharenko A.D. The need for orthopedic treatment with removable plate dentures among the rural population Proceedings of the VI Congress of the Russian Dental Association. - M., 2000.
- Doynikov A.I. Replacement of dentition defects with bridge prostheses Guide to orthopedic dentistry / Ed. L.V. Ilyina-Markosyan. - M., 1974.
- Lea, F. M. (1970). "The Chemistry of Cement and Concrete." Chemical Publishing Company.
- Hewlett, P. C. (2003). "Lea's Chemistry of Cement and Concrete." Elsevier Science.
- Taylor, H. F. W. (1990). "Cement Chemistry." Academic Press.
- Mindess, S., Young, J. F., & Darwin, D. (2003). "Concrete." Prentice Hall.
- Сейтмуратова, В. Ш., & Алеуова, Р. Ш. ЕО IPSO. *ЕО IPSO Учредители: Издательство " Научная артель"*, (6), 123-125.
- Сейтмуратова, В. Ш., & Алеуова, Р. Ш. МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЕ МЕТОДЫ В ПРАКТИЧЕСКОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ. *НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ «ЕО IPSO»*, 123.
- Алламбергенова, М. (2010). Использование интерактивных учебных комплексов в процессе высшего образования как средство формирования творческой атмосферы. *Образование.–Алмата*, (6), 132-134.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Kh, A. M. : ADVANTAGES OF USING E-LEARNING RESOURCES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *International journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research*, 9, 5-9.
- Allambergenova, M., Kunnazarov, A., & Kazbekova, E. (2020). Creation of pedagogical software for practical Training in computer science. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(12), 86-91.
- Алламбергенова, М. Х. (2010). Методика использования интерактивных учебных комплексов по курсу информатика и информационные технологии. *Молодой ученый*, (8-2), 142-145.
- Алламбергенова, М. Х., & Жугинисова, Ж. И. (2023). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИ ТАРБИЯЛАНУВЧИЛАРИГА ЭЛЕМЕНТАР МАТЕМАТИК ТУШУНЧАЛАРНИ ЎРГАТИШДА ДАСТУРИЙ ВОСИТАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. *QUALITY OF TEACHER EDUCATION UNDER MODERN CHALLENGES*, 1(1), 72-76.
- Утепбергенова, А. Т., & Аллаамбергенова, М. (2018). РАЗВИТИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОГО ОБЩЕСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *Донецкие чтения 2018: образование, наука, инновации, культура и вызовы современности* (pp. 394-395).
- Khasanbaevna, A. M. Creation of Multimedia Electronic Educational Methodological Complexes for the Course of Informatics. *JournalNX*, 111-116.
- Саламова, Ф., & Розымова, Ы. (2019). Особенности развития аутичного ребенка. *Вестник Донского государственного аграрного университета*, (2-2), 42-46.
- Salamova, F. S. (2023). METHODOLOGY OF STUDYING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CORRECTIVE EXERCISES IN SCHOOLS OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING DEFECTS. *Confrencea*, 5(05), 159-161.
- Feruza, S. (2021). Increasing the Efficiency of Corrective Training in Special Educational Institutions. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(10), 207-208.
- Lobar, J., & Feruza, S. (2022). Ways to conduct lessons for children with speech disabilities with innovative technologies. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 4, 36-39.
- Hakimbekovna, S. F. (2022). Improving correctional technology for deaf and hard of hearing children. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 4, 31-35.
- Тасбаева, Г., & Саламова, Ф. (2020). ПОДГОТОВКА БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ-ЛОГОПЕДОВ К САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. *НАУЧНЫЙ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ «АКАДЕМИЧЕСКАЯ ПУБЛИЦИСТИКА»*, 434.
- Саламова, Ф. Х. (2020). РОЛЬ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ-ДЕФЕКТОЛОГОВ. In *ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ЗНАНИЯМИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ* (pp. 166-168).
- Tursinbaevish, S. A. (2023). BOLALARDA NUTQ MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 25(1), 168-170.
- Abdullaevna, T. K., Amangeldievna, B. A., Berdibaevna, D. G., & Tursinbaevich, S. A. (1971). Speech Deficiencies In Preschool Children And Methods Of Correcting Them. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.
- Tursinbaevish, S. A. (2023). XALQ DOSTONLARINING O'RGATISHNI AMALIY ANAMIYATI ("ALPOMISH" DOSTONI MISOLIDA). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 26(2), 74-78.
- Nukus, S. A. T. (2022). Educating young people on manners in folk epics. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 11(10), 107-110.
- Saparov, A. T. Educating Young People to Patriotism in the Epic "Forty Girls". *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(11), 137-139.
- Tursinbaevich, S. A. (2023). THE ISSUES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 2(11), 308-311.
- Ruzimova, I. (2023). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARDA KREATIVLIK KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(12), 57-60.
- RIZAEV, S. (2021). THE INFLUENCE OF AGRO-TECHNICAL AND CHEMICAL WEEDS CONTROL MEASURES AND YIELD OF AUTUMN WHEAT IN ZARAFSHON VALLEY OF UZBEKISTAN. *PLANT CELL BIOTECHNOLOGY AND MOLECULAR BIOLOGY*, 38-46.
- Буриев, А. А., & Орипов, Р. (2018). Влияние предшественников на урожайность озимой пшеницы в условиях орошаемых типичных серозёмов. In *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS* (pp. 254-256).

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Abdirazzakovich, B. A. (2022). Effects of intercropping on soil fertility and yield of winter wheat. *The Peerian Journal*, 13, 80-82.
- Abdirazzakovich, B. A., & Razzak, O. (2022). EFFECT OF PREVIOUS CROPS ON SOIL FERTILITY AND WINTER WHEAT YIELD. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(12), 723-727.
- Abdirazzakovich, B. A. (2021). The Role of Sideration in Short-crop Rotation. *European Journal of Agricultural and Rural Education*, 2(11), 36-38.
- Shamsiddinovna, A. M. (2023). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TODAY'S SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 3(11), 155-159.
- Мухсиева, А., & Хуррамов, С. (2023). О 'quvchilarda ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning mazmunı. *Цифровизация современного образования: проблема и решение*, 1(1), 83-87.
- Мухсиева, А., & Нурбекова, Н. (2023). Во 'lajak tarbiya fani o 'qituvchisi tayorlashda tarbiya texnologiyalardan foydalanish. *Цифровизация современного образования: проблема и решение*, 1(1), 72-75.
- Shamsiddinovna, A. M. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARNI O'QITISHDA INTERFAOL METODIK QO'LLANMALARDAN FOYDALANISH. *Ustozlar uchun*, 41(1), 206-208.
- Shamsitdinovna, M. A., & Ulugbekovna, N. N. (2023). DIDACTIC TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'SOCIAL COMPETENCE. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44, 4224-4228.
- Mukhsieva, A., & Juramurotova, S. (2023). IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY BASED ON VIRTUAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES. *Science and innovation*, 2(B3), 26-29.
- Mukhsieva, A., & Norbutayev, F. (2023). FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE AS A PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 443-446.
- Мухсиева, А. Ш. (2022). ПЕДАГОГИКО-КВАЛИМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У УЧАЩИХСЯ: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres.2022.10.10.010>
- Мухсиева Азиза Шамситдиновна доцент кафедры «Педагогика» Ташкентского государственного педагогического университета имени Низами, доктор педагогических наук. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (10), 103-107.
- Sh, M. A., & Samatova, I. A. (2022). Method of Using Vitagen Educational Technologies in the Development of Social Competences of Students. *Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 1(4), 90-95.
- Aziza, M., & IA, S. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF VITAGEN LEARNING TECHNOLOGY. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(4).
- Aziza, M., & Sahobar, S. (2022). OILADA FARZAND TARBIYASI DAVLAT SIYOSATIDAGI USTIVOR MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, (Special Issue 2), 346-349.
- Muxsiyeva, A., & Qizi, A. M. F. M. (2022). ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA BO'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNI TYUTORLIK VA FASILITATORLIK FAOLIYATIGA TAYYORLASH. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, (Special Issue 1), 146-148.
- Shamsitdinovna, M. A. (2022). Local-modular technology for developing social competencies in students.
- Буриев, Х. Ч., & Енилеев, Н. Ш. (2014). Учеты и фенологические наблюдения при проведении опытов с плодовыми и ягодными культурами.
- Зокиров, Х. Х., Нормуратов, О. У., Жураев, Э. Б., Алматов, Б. Т., Муратов, М. Ш., & Кадиоров, М. А. (2015). Влияние полифосфатов на рост, развитие вегетативных и генеративных органов хлопчатника. In *Наука сегодня: теоретические и практические аспекты* (pp. 207-214).
- Жураев, Э. Б., & Буриев, Х. Ч. (2018). Влияние регуляторов роста на качество укоренения черенков и развитие саженцев маслины (*Olea Europa* L.). *Молодой ученый*, (39), 54-57.
- Жураев, Э. Б., & Буриев, Х. Ч. (2018). Способы повышения зимостойкости маслины в условиях сухих субтропиков Узбекистана. *Молодой ученый*, (39), 57-60.
- Jurayev, E. B. (2022). OLIVE (*Olea*.) PFLANZE-NUTZEN DER NATUR. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 1(7), 39-42.
- Jurayev, E., Usmonov, Y., & Kenjayev, R. (2022). BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF THE OLIVE PLANT (*Olea*.), SIGNIFICANCE IN FOLK MEDICINE. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 370-372.
- Jurayev, E. B., & Toshpo'Latov, A. S. (2022). ANOR YETISHTIRISHDA OZUQA ELEMENTLARIGA BO'LGAN TALAB. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 4-2), 969-973.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Jurayev, E., Usmonov, Y., & Kenjayev, R. (2022). ZAYTUN (Olea.) O'SIMLIGINING BIOLOGIYASI VA DORIVORLIK XUSUSIYATLARI, XALQ TABOBATIDAGI ANAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1(D8), 370-372.
- БУРИЕВ, Х., ЕНИЛЕЕВ, Н., & ЖУРАЕВ, Э. (2018). ОСОБЕННОСТИ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ КОРНЕВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ МАСЛИНЫ В ЮВЕНИЛЬНОМ ПЕРИОДЕ. *ЎЗБЕКИСТОН АГРАР ФАНИ ХАБАРНОМАСИ*, 65.
- Жураев, Э. Б. (2018). ИНТЕНСИФИКАЦИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ САЖЕНЦЕВ МАСЛИНЫ ИЗ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ЧЕРЕНКОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ РЕГУЛЯТОРОВ РОСТА. In *ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ НАУКИ, ОБЩЕСТВА, ПРОИЗВОДСТВА И ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ* (pp. 104-106).
- Жураев, Э. Б. (2018). КАЧЕСТВА УКОРЕНЕНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ЧЕРЕНКОВ МАСЛИНЫ ОТ ЗАВИСИМОСТЬ СХЕМЫ РАЗМЕЩЕНИЯ САЖЕНЦЕВ. In *Инновационные подходы в современной науке* (pp. 55-58).
- Зокиров, Х. Х., Алматов, Б. Т., Нормуратов, О. У., Жураев, Э. Б., Муратов, М. Ш., & Кадилов, М. А. (2015). Технология и урожайность озимой пшеницы. In *Наука сегодня: теоретические и практические аспекты* (pp. 214-219).
- Енилеев, Н. Ш., Жураев, Э. Б., & Буриев, Х. Ч. (2014). ОСОБЕННОСТИ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ СОРТОВ МАСЛИНЫ ИНТРОДУЦИРОВАННЫХ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Вестник Прикаспия*, (3), 19-22.
- Chutbaevich, B. N., Bakhtiyorovich, J. E., & Ugli, A. S. B. Stability of Plants of Fruit Crops to Low Temperatures in the Conditions of Dry Subtropics of Uzbekistan. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(1), 42-47.
- Жураев, Э. Б., ХУДОЙБЕРДИЕВ, Э. Б. Ў., НОРМАХМАТОВ, С. Ш. Ў., & УСМОНОВ, Ю. У. Ў. ТОЧНАЯ НАУКА. *ТОЧНАЯ НАУКА Учредители: ИП Никитин Игорь Анатольевич*, (127), 9-12.
- Himmatova, N. N. (2023). Psychological Aspects of Learning a Foreign Language. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 13, 1-6.
- Himmatova, N. (2023). THE PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECT IN THE STUDY OF ENGLISH FOR 1ST YEAR STUDENTS. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(1), 17-22.
- Himmatova, N. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(1), 16-19.
- Himmatova, N. (2022). GENDER EQUALITY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and innovation*, 1(C7), 118-120.
- Himmatova Nodira Normamatovna (2022) PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS THE IMPORTANCE OF A DESCRIPTIVE DICTIONARY IN INDEPENDENT LEARNING OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE 1, 60-64
- Himmatova Nodira Normamatovna (2022) XOTIN-QIZLARNI IJTIMOIIY SIYOSIY VA IQTISODIY FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALARNI O'RGANISH O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI XABARLARI
- Normamatovna, H. N. (2023). GEOMETRIK MAZMUNDAGI AMALIY HARAКТERDAGI MASALALARNI YECHISHNI O'RGATISH METODIKASI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 27(1), 54-57.
- Normamatovna, H. N. GEOMETRIK MAZMUNDAGI AMALIY HARAКТERDAGI MASALALARNI YECHISHNI O'RGATISH METODIKASI.
- Khimmatova, N. (2023). Psychological Mechanisms in Teaching English. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(7), 511-515. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/488>
- Normamatovna, H. N. (2023). IMPROVING THE SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION PROCESS IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 57-61.
- Himmatova, N. N. (2023). THE EFFECT OF PERSONAL STANDARDS ON THE PROCESS OF ECONOMIC SOCIALIZATION OF THE POPULATION. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(7), 377-386.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2022). Processes of formation of intellectual abilities of preschool children by means of innovative technologies. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 7, 73-74.
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2016). Особенности Организации Взаимодействия Дошкольного Образовательного Учреждения С Семьями Воспитанников. *Вестник современной науки*, (6-2), 19-22.
- Altboeva, G. (2021). Processes Of Formation Intellectual Abilities of Preschool Teachers Through Innovative Technologies. *Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3, 18-21.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2016). инновационная деятельность в детских дошкольных учреждениях. *Вестник современной науки*, (6-2), 15-18.
- Altibaeva, G. M. (2020). IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF CHILDRENS SPEECH DEVELOPMENT THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS OF FUTURE EDUCATORS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (7), 82-84.
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2016). Подготовка детей в школе в условиях дошкольногообразовательного учреждения. *Евразийский научный журнал*, (6), 459-461.
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2018). Анализ программ по организации нравственного воспитания и формированию культуры поведения. *Вопросы педагогики*, (2), 7-9.
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2017). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА СЕМЬИ И ДОШКОЛЬНОГО УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДЕТЕЙ. *Вестник современной науки*, (2-2), 20-22.
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2020). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ ТАШКИЛОТИДА INNOVATION FAOLIYATNI YO'LGA QO'YISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ*, (SI-2.№ 3).
- Алтибаева, Г. М. (2018). ОСНОВНЫЕ УСЛОВИЯ И СРЕДСТВА РАЗВИТИЯ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТВОРЧЕСТВА ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (6), 74-76.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2023). INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR VOSITASIDA MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI INTELLEKTUAL QOBILIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH IJTIMOY-MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(6 (INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHER)), 303-310.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2023, September). MECHANISMS OF FORMING THE INTELLECTUAL ABILITY OF PRE-SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 43-44).
- Majitovna, A. G., & Qizi, X. Y. B. (2023). OILADA MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA OTA VA ONANING TOLERANTLIK MUNOSABATI DARAJASINI ANIQLASHNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK TAHLILI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(9), 1789-1793.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA TA'LIM BERISHDA KOMPETENSIYAVIY YONDOSHUV. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(9), 1784-1788.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2023). INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARBIYALANUVCHILARNI INTELLEKTUAL QOBILIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA ULARNING YOSHIGA XOS BO'LGAN PEDAGOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 3(29), 36-41.
- Majitovna, A. G., & Koltorayevna, E. X. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MEHNAT TARBIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MAZMUNI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 3(29), 46-52.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS SPECIFIC TO THEIR AGE IN FORMING THE INTELLECTUAL ABILITY OF THE STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(5), 414-418.
- Majitovna, A. G. (2022). Psychological and pedagogical features of their age in the formation of intellectual abilities of students on the basis of innovative technologies. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 20-25.
- Шаева, Р., & Шомуродов, К. (2021). Пути оптимизации комплексного лечения гнойно воспалительных заболеваний челюстно-лицевой области (обзор литературы). *Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований*, 2(2), 13-17.
- Gayratovna, S. R. (2022). The Course of the Wound Process in Purulent-Inflammatory Diseases of the Maxillofacial Region. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 3(4), 255-259.
- Шомуродов, К. Э., Мирхусанова, Р. С., & Шаева, Р. Г. (2021). Ошибки в диагностике острых воспалительных заболеваний периапикальных тканей в догоспитальном периоде. In *Стоматология-наука и практика, перспективы развития* (pp. 247-249).
- Shaeva, R. G., Shomurodov, K. E., & Bekmurodov, E. E. (2023). Перспективы применения трансплантатов из щёчной области в хирургическом лечении врождённых расщелин нёба. *Integrative dentistry and maxillofacial surgery*, 2(3 (5)), 9-15.
- Шаева, Р. (2023). ОБЗОРНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВРОЖДЁННОЙ РАСЩЕЛИНЫ НЁБА. *MedUnion*.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Шаева, Р. Г. (2022). ДИНАМИКА СОСТОЯНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ БУХАРСКОГО РЕГИОНА. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 747-751.
- Азимов, М. И., Шомуродов, К. Э., Шаева, Р. Г., & Мирхусанова, Р. С. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАННЕЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ОСТРЫХ ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПЕРИАПИКАЛЬНЫХ ТКАНЕЙ И ИХ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ. *Журнал " Медицина и инновации "*, (2), 211-220.
- Gayratovna, S. R. (2022). WAYS OF OPTIMIZATION OF LOCAL THERAPY FOR PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE MAXILLOFAQIAL REGION. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(8), 16-21.
- Шаева, Р., & Шомуродов, К. (2022). Оптимизация комплексного лечения гнойно-воспалительных заболеваний челюстно-лицевой области. *Дни молодых учёных*, (1), 125-126.
- Шаева, Р., & Шомуродов, К. (2022). МОНИТОРИНГ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ ГНОЙНОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ ЧЕЛЮСТНОЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ В БУХАРСКОМ РЕГИОНЕ. *Журнал " Медицина и инновации "*, (3), 452-458.
- Шаева, Р., & Абдурахманов, М. (2021). Иммунокорректирующая терапии в комплексном лечении флегмон челюстно-лицевой области. *Актуальные проблемы стоматологии и челюстно-лицевой хирургии* 4, 1(01), 116-117.
- Шаева, Р. Г., & Шомуродов, К. Э. НОВЫЙ ДЕНЬ В МЕДИЦИНЕ. *НОВЫЙ ДЕНЬ В МЕДИЦИНЕ Учредители: Бухарский государственный медицинский институт, ООО " Новый день в медицине "*, (2), 193-196.
- Абдулхамидова, Х., & Эшкораев, С. (2022). НОВЫЕ ЦЕМЕНТНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(4), 28-31.
- Eshqorayev, S., Abdulhamidova, H., & Abdulhamidov, J. (2022). SEMENT KLINKER TO'PLAMLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISH: CaO-SiO₂-Al₂O₃-SO₃-CaCl₂-MgO. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(12), 955-958.
- Эшкараев, С. Ч., Тураев, Х. Х., & Эшкараев, С. С. (2021). ВЛИЯНИЕ ГЕКСАХЛОРЦИКЛОГЕКСАНА НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ РАДИОАКТИВНОСТИ В ПОЧВАХ СУРХАНДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. In *СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ХИМИЧЕСКАЯ ФИЗИКА НА СТЫКЕ ФИЗИКИ, ХИМИИ И БИОЛОГИИ* (pp. 399-400).
- Эшкараев, С. Ч., Тураев, Х. Х., & Бабамуратов, Б. Э. (2021). РАДИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА РАДИОНУКЛИДОВ В ПОЧВАХ ЮЖНЫХ РЕГИОНОВ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 290-319).
- Abdulhamidova, H., Eshkoraev, S., & Javgashev, Y. (2022). TECHNOLOGY OF SILICATE BRICK PRODUCTION. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(4), 8-11.
- Eshqorayev, S. S., & Ro'zimurodov, B. I. (2022). AHOLI YASHASH XONADONLARIDA IS GAZIDAN NIMOYALOVCHI FILTRLAR TAYYORLASH. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 2(6), 209-212.
- Xaydarova, M. D., Eshqorayev, S. S., & Ro'Zimurodov, B. I. (2022). Kaliy ma'danlarining dunyo bo'yicha uchrashi. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 149-151.
- Eshqorayev, S. S., Ro'zimurodov, B. I., & Choriyeva, M. S. (2022). YOSHLARNI ILM-FAN VA INNOVATSIYALARGA QIZIQTIRISHNING NOAN'ANAVIY USULI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(6), 308-310.
- Xaydarova, M. D., Eshqorayev, S. S., & Ro'zimurodov, B. I. (2022). TYUBEGATAN KONINING SILVINITLARINI ERITISH JARAYONINI O'RGANISH. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(9), 37-39.
- Eshqorayev, S. S., & Choriyeva, M. S. (2022). Tog'-kon sanoatida texnologiya va uning ishga ta'sirini tushunish. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 24, 237-239.
- Eshkoraev, S., Turaev, K., & Eshkoraev, S. (2021). Influence of Pesticides on Increasing Soil Radioactivity. *World*, 6(4), 49-54.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Davronovna, K. M., Sadridinovich, E. S., & Yigitali Jo'ra o'g, J. (2022). Dependence of Karst Processes on Physico-Chemical Properties of Salts. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(9), 25-28.
- Eshkoraev, S., Abdulhamidova, H., & Javgashev, Y. (2022). INGREDIENT OF PORTLAND CEMENT. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(9), 21-23.
- Choriyeva, M. S., & Eshkoraev, S. S. (2022). The interaction of energy with climate change. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 04 (108), 60-63.
- Uralov, N. B., Turaev, H. Kh., Eshkarayev, S. Ch., & Eshqorayev, S.S. (2021). Analysis of graphene properties, production and application. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 11 (103), 726-728.
- SURXONDARYO VILOYATI TUPROQLARIDAGI SEZIY-137 RADIONUKLIDI BETA NURLANISH AKTIVLIGINI RADIOMETRIK-SPEKTROMETRIK USULDA ANIQLASH 1 Eshkoraev S.Ch., 2To'rayev X.X., 2Umbarov I.A., 2 Babamuratov B.E., 1 Eshqorayev S.S. 1 Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti Termiz filiali. 2Termiz davlat universiteti
- S. Eshkoraev, S. Eshqorayev, H. Abdulhamidova, & J. Abdulhamidov (2022). VODOROD ISHLAB CHIQRISH: ELEKTROLIZ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (A8), 360-365. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7391172
- Akhatov, A. A., Eshkoraev, S. Ch., Normurodova, Kh. D., & Eshkoraev, S. S. (2021). Study of the influence of graphene nanofillers on the properties of composites based on polypropylene. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 10 (102), 816-818.
- Sadrididdin o'g'li, E. S., Soatmurod o'g'li, A. A., & Soatmurodovna, S. R. N. (2023). IONITLAR (SORBENTLAR) YORDAMIDA ERITMADAN OLTINNI SORBSIYALASH USULIDA AJRATIB OLISH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(1), 6-11.
- Choriyeva, M. S. qizi, & Eshqorayev, S. S. o'g'li. (2022). MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIK VA DINIY BAG'RIKENGLIK O'ZBEK XALQINING YUKSAK QADRIYATIDIR. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING, 1(3), 46-51. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/iclt/article/view/2879>
- Eshqorayev, S., & Abdulhamidova, H. (2023). UNCONVENTIONAL METHOD OF CEMENT PRODUCTION BY ADDING NEW SUBSTANCES TO CLINKER IN PORTLAND CEMENT PRODUCTION. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(4), 136-142. Retrieved from <https://internationalbulletins.com/intjour/index.php/ibet/article/view/542>
- Abdulhamidova, H., Eshkoraev, S., & Choriyeva, M. (2022). MINERAL RESOURCES. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 2(9), 21-23. Retrieved from <https://internationalbulletins.com/intjour/index.php/ibet/article/view/39>
- Sadrididdin o'g'li, E. S., & Sherzod qizi, A. H. (2023). Development of a Solar Panel-Based Electrolysis Device for Hydrogen Production. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 17, 94-98. Retrieved from <http://sjii.indexedresearch.org/index.php/sjii/article/view/801>
- Sadrididdin o'g'li, E. S., Soatmurodovna, S. R. N., & Soatmurod o'g'li, A. A. IONITLAR (SORBENTLAR) YORDAMIDA ERITMADAN OLTINNI SORBSIYALASH USULIDA AJRATIB OLISH.
- Khaydarova munira davronovna, eshqorayev samariddin sadrididdin o'g'li, boltayeva iroda yusuf qizi & allazov rustam yo'ldosho'g'li. *journal of engineering and technology (jet) issn(p):2250-2394; issn(e): applied vol. 13, issue 1, jun 2023, 139-142 tjprc pvt. ltd. study of the melting process of sylvinites of tubegatan mine.*
- Eshqorayev Samariddin Sadrididdin o'g'li, & Abdulhamidova Hilola Sherzod qizi. (2023). FORMING A SENSE OF TOLERANCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR, 1(5), 167-181. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itftdm/article/view/1299>
- Эшқараев Садриддин Чориевич, Абдулхамидова Хилола Шерзод кизи, & Эшқараев Самариддин Садриддин ўғли. (2022). Радиохимия: всесторонний обзор ключевых концепций и приложений. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(1), 10-13. Retrieved from <http://mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/11>
- Эшқараев Садриддин Чориевич, Абдулхамидова Хилола Шерзод кизи, & Эшқараев Самариддин Садриддин ўғли. (2023). СИЛИКОНЫ: ХИМИЯ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ УНИВЕРСАЛЬНЫХ ПОЛИМЕРОВ. *International Conference on Multidisciplinary Science*, 1(1), 4-6. Retrieved from <http://mjstjournal.com/index.php/icms/article/view/2>
- Abdulhamidova Hilola Sherzod qizi, & Eshqorayev Samariddin Sadrididdin o'g'li. (2023). Innovative Methods of Ammonia Production: A Review. *Web of Semantics : Journal of Interdisciplinary Science*, 1(1), 18-24. Retrieved from <http://web.semanticjournals.org/index.php/wos/article/view/5>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Shaymanova, R. S., Urazov, M. K., Samariddin, E., Yuldosheva, D. N., & Shaymanova, N. X. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF DRILLING FLUID FOR CONSTRUCTION OF WELLS IN ARCTIC SHELF WATER. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(2), 8-11.
- Rakhmankulov, J. E., & Eshkoraev, S. S. (2023). STUDY OF CELLULOSE EXTRACTION PROCESSES SUITABLE FOR OBTAINING LOW-QUANTITY PRODUCTS FROM THE STEM PART OF THE LOCAL SAFLOR PLANT. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(10), 717-723.
- Rakhmankulov, J. E., & Eshkoraev, S. S. (2023). INVESTIGATION OF SEVERAL BRANDS OF CELLULOSE SUITABLE FOR OBTAINING ORGANIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS FROM CANNABIS PLANT STEM. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 198-203.
- Eshkoraev, S. (2024). PORTLAND CEMENT COMPOSITION, PROPERTIES, AND APPLICATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 250-263.
- Холмуродов, М. П., Тураев, Х. Х., Эшкараев, С. Ч., & Сафаров, А. М. (2021). РАДИОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ РАДИОНУКЛИДОВ В ПРИРОДНЫХ ВОДАХ СУРХАНДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *Universum: химия и биология*, (5-2 (83)), 36-39.
- Бозоров, Л. У., Тураев, Х. Х., Касимов, Ш. А., & Эшкараев, С. Ч. (2021). СИНТЕЗ НОВЫХ СОРБЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОЛИВИНИЛХЛОРИДА, МОДИФИЦИРОВАННОГО ДИЭТИЛАМИНОМ. *Universum: химия и биология*, (5-2), 5-8.
- Тураев, Х. Х., Эшмуродов, Х. Э., & Эшкараев, С. Ч. (2021). ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ КАМЕННОЙ БУМАГИ НА ОСНОВЕ ИЗВЕСТНЯКА ШАРГУНСКОГО И БАЙСУНСКОГО МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЙ. *Universum: химия и биология*, (5-2), 14-17.
- ESHKARAEV, S. C., BABAMURATOV, B. E., KHAYDAROVA, Z. E., BOBOMUROTOV, N. N., & NORMAMATOV, N. D. (2021). WAYS OF PLANT DEFINITION OF RADIO NUCLEAR-LOCED SOILS OF UZBEKISTAN. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 517-522.
- TURAEV, K. K., ABDIKADIROV, S. A., ESHKARAEV, S. C., & DZHUMAIEVA, Z. E. (2021). DETERMINATION OF THE PRESENCE OF RADIONUCLIDE RADON-222 IN THE ATMOSPHERIC AIR OF THE SURKHANDARYA REGION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 345-349.
- Sadridin, E., Nemat, N., Murod, R., Zafar, M., & Abdulla, M. (2020). Radiometric determination of the presence of caesium-137 and strontium-90 radionuclides in products of the fodder industry. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(11), 411-417.
- Sadridin, E., Nurmamat, B., Azamat, S., Sarvara, C., & Mahmatkarim, K. (2020). Radiometric determination of the presence of cesium-137 and strontium-90 radionuclides in food. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(11), 404-410.
- KHOLMURODOV, M. P., TURAEV, K. K., & ESHKARAEV, S. C. (2021). RADIO METRIC DETERMINATION OF THORIUM-232 RADIONUCLIDE IN THE WATERS OF THE SHERABAD RIVER IN SURKHANDARYA REGION. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 350-354.
- TILLAEV, K. R., ESHKARAEV, S. C., & BABAMURATOV, B. E. (2021). SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE WATERS OF THE SURKHANDARYA RIVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR DETERMINATION OF HEAVY TOXIC METALS. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 471-475.
- Khayit, T., Makhmatkarim, K., Shavkat, A., & Sadridin, E. (2020). Radiometric determination of radon-222 in the atmospheric air of the city of termeza, republic of uzbekistan. *European journal of molecular & clinical medicine*, 7(11), 397-403.
- Eshkaraev, S., Turaev, K., & Eshkoraev, S. (2021). Influence of Pesticides on Increasing Soil Radioactivity. *World*, 6(4), 49-54.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Uralov, N. B., Turaev, H. Kh., Eshkarayev, S. Ch., & Eshqorayev, S.S. (2021). Analysis of graphene properties, production and application. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 11 (103), 726-728.
- SURXONDARYO VILOYATI TUPROQLARIDAGI SEZIY-137 RADIONUKLIDI BETA NURLANISH AKTIVLIGINI RADIOMETRIK-SPEKTROMETRIK USULDA ANIQLASH I Eshkaraev S.Ch., 2To'rayev X.X., 2Umbarov I.A., 2 Babamuratov B.E., 1 Eshqorayev S.S. I Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti Termiz filiali. 2Termiz davlat universiteti
- S. Eshkaraev, S. Eshqorayev, H. Abdulhamidova, & J. Abdulhamidov (2022). VODOROD ISHLAB CHIQRISH: ELEKTROLIZ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (A8), 360-365. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7391172
- Akhatov, A. A., Eshkaraev, S. Ch., Normurodova, Kh. D., & Eshkoraev, S. S. (2021). Study of the influence of graphene nanofillers on the properties of composites based on polypropylene. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 10 (102), 816-818.
- Эшкароев, С. Ч., Тураев, Х. Х., & Бабамуратов, Б. Э. (2021). РАДИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА РАДИОНУКЛИДОВ В ПОЧВАХ ЮЖНЫХ РЕГИОНОВ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 290-319).
- Eshkaraev S.Ch., Turaev X.X. Radiometricheskoe opredelenie s-137 v pochvax Surxandarinskoy oblasti Respubliki Uzbekistan s pomoshyu beta-i gamma-izlucheniyy //M. Universum. – 2020. - №. 6. - S. 124-129.
- Turaev X.X., Eshkaraev S.Ch. Radiometricheskoe opredelenie strontsiya-90 v pochvax Surxandar'inskoy oblasti s pomoshyu beta-i gamma-izlucheniyy //T. NamDU. – 2020. - №. 6.
- Turaev X.X., Eshkaraev S.Ch. Radiometricheskoe opredelenie tseziya-137 i strontsiya v pochvax Surxandarinskoy oblasti s pomoshyu bloka detektora BDEG-80 //T. SamDU. – 2020. - №. 9.
- Inoyatova Nazokat Qahramon qizi, & Eshkaraev Sadridin Choriyevich. (2023). ICHIMLIK SUVIDA RADIOFAOL ELEMENTLARNING PAYDO BO'LISHI VA INSON SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIRI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(3), 72–79. Retrieved from <http://universalpublishings.com/index.php/jusr/article/view/308>
- Umirqulova Feruza Abdisamatovna, & Eshkaraev Sadridin Choriyevich. (2023). YOVOYOI O'SIMLIKLAR TARKIBIDAN DORIVOR MODDALARNI EKSTRAKTSIYON AJRATIB OLISH USULLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(4), 86–92. Retrieved from <http://universalpublishings.com/index.php/jusr/article/view/413>
- Pardayev Anvar Misirovich, & Eshkaraev Sadridin Choriyevich. (2023). STOMATOLOGIYADA YADROVIY TIBBIYOTNI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(4), 69–75. Retrieved from <http://universalpublishings.com/index.php/jusr/article/view/410>
- Amonov, N. A., Ch, E. S., & Abduraimova, G. N. (2022). Analysis of Research on the Properties, Production and Use of Carbon Nanoparticles. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 136-138.
- Akromov, A. A., & Mehridinova, A. G. (2022). TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A CREATIVE APPROACH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 639-642.
- Mexridinova, A. G. (2021). INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FINE ARTS CLASSES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 351-354.
- Sheraliyevna, S. S. (2023). ABDURAUF FITRATNING "OILA" ASARIDAGI MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY QARASHLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(5), 352-362.
- Abdulloyevna, M. Z. (2023). SHARQ MUTAFAKKIRLARINING MA'NAVIY TARBIYA HAQIDAGI TA'LIMOTLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(5), 340-351.
- Baxtiyor O'g'li, Q. J. (2023). ZAMONAVIY O'QITUVCHIGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(5), 1256-1263.
- Yunusovich, A. V., Ahmedov, F., Norboyev, K., & Zakirov, F. (2022). Analysis of Experimental Research Results Focused on Improving Student Psychological Health. *International Journal of Modern Education & Computer Science*, 14(2).
- Yunusovich, A. V. The Research Results Analysis of Higher Educational Institutions on Students' Psychological Health. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 169-176.
- TA, O. V. O. R. M., & VAZIRLIGI, L. SOTSIAL PSIXOLOGIYA: MENEJMENT VA MARKETING PSIXOLOGIYASI FANIDAN O'QUV-USLUBIYMAJMUA.
- TA, O. V. O. R. M., & VAZIRLIGI, L. SOTSIAL PSIXOLOGIYA FANIDAN O'QUV-USLUBIYMAJMUA.
- Xalbayeva, G. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI MAKTABGA TAYYORLASHDA PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARDAN FOYDALANISH. *Журнал Педагогике и психологии в современном образовании*, (1).

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Arshidinovna K. G. . (2023). Scientific and Methodological Foundations of Preparing Children for School. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 34, 85–95. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1259>
- Xalbayeva Gulnoza. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR BILISH JARAYONLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA SENSOR TARBIYANING O'RNI. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(7), 163–172. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/418>
- Arshidinova, X. G. (2022). BOLALARNI MAKTABNING BOSHLANGICH TA'LIM BOSQICHIGA TAYYORLASHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHISHNING DOLZARBLIGI. *FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI*, 379-382.
- Калинина, О. Н. РОЛЬ РЕЧЕВЫХ СИТУАЦИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ УЗБЕКСКИХ ГРУПП.
- Mirzayeva, F. O., & Abulova, M. K. (2023). PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(12), 548-552.
- Abulova, M. K. (2023). The Concept of the Family in Modern Society and its Main Tasks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 20, 47-51.
- Abulova, M. K. (2023). THE ROLE OF LEGAL EDUCATION IN REFORMING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 22, 39-40.
- Тилеумуратова, Б. А. (2015). Ресурсоведческая характеристика некоторых видов лекарственных растений в Каракалпакстане. *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*, (5-6), 21-23.
- Халмуратов, П., Кутлымуратова, Г. А., & Романова, Л. К. (2017). Биоэкологические особенности атропелладонна. При интродукции в условиях Каракалпакстана. *Вестник науки и образования*, 1(3 (27)), 30-32.
- Кутлымуратова, Г. А. (2013). К вопросу интродукции лекарственных растений в условиях Республики Каракалпакстан. *Аспирант и соискатель*, (4), 88-90.
- Косназаров, К. А., Кутлымуратова, Г. А., & Романова, Л. К. (2013). АНТРОПОГЕННОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ РАСТЕНИЙ MATRICARIA L. И ИХ ФИТОЦЕНОЗОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН. *SCIENCE AND WORLD*, 59.
- Ochildiyevna, Y. M., & Vozorovna, C. S. (2023). TABIAT BILAN TANISHTIRISH ORQALI BOLALAR NUTQINI O'STIRISH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 621-624.
- Ochildiyevna, Y. M. (2023). Pedagogical skill of the educator. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 20, 5-7.
- Ochildiyevna, Y. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI TABIAT BILAN TANISHTIRISH. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 17(1), 160-164.
- Ochildiyevna, Y. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTIDA SAHNALASHTIRISH FAOLIYATINING ANAMIYATI. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 6(2), 295-298.
- Ochildiyevna, Y. M., & Achildiyevna, S. F. (2023). MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR INTRODUCING SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN TO NATURE.
- Mehriniso, Y. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TALIM YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MADANIY XULQ ATVORNI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук*, 2(2), 255-259.
- Акрамова, Ф. Д., Шакарбаев, У. А., Акбаров, А. А., Уббиниязова, Ж. К., Торемуратов, М. Ш., Сапаров, К. А., & Азимов, Д. А. (2023). ГЕЛЬМИНТОФАУНА ПОЛОРОГИХ (ARTIODACTYLA: BOVIDAE) СЕВЕРО-ЗАПАДНОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (24), 40-45.
- Шакарбаев, У. А., Акрамова, Ф. Д., & Азимов, Д. А. (2016). Церкарии трематод моллюсков (Gastropoda, Pulmonata) Северо-востока Узбекистана. *ББК 28.083 Т65 Ответственный редактор доктор биологических наук СО Мовсеян*, 197.
- Хамрокулова, З. Х., Сапаров, К. А., & Акрамова, Ф. Д. ГЕЛЬМИНТЫ СИНАНТРОПНЫХ ГРЫЗУНОВ СЕВЕРО-ВОСТОКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *Biologiya*, 19.
- Акрамова, Ф. Д., Хамрокулова, З. Х., Мирзаева, У. А., & Сапаров, К. А. ГЕЛЬМИНТОФАУНА ГРЫЗУНОВ (RODENTIA: SCIURIDAE, MURIDAE) СЕВЕРО-ВОСТОКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *ЁШИ ОЛИМЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ*, 27.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Мирзаева, А. У., Ярмухамедова, Н. А., Акрамова, Ф. Д., Камолходжаев, Д. А., Шапаотов, Р. К., & Эсонбоев, Ж. Р. IXODOIDEA КАНАЛАРНИНГ ЮҚУМЛИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАР ТАРҚАТИШИДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ.
- ШАКАРБАЕВ, У., АКРАМОВА, Ф., & АЗИМОВ, Д. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА БОРЬБЫ С ПАРАЗИТАРНЫМИ БОЛЕЗНЯМИ. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА БОРЬБЫ С ПАРАЗИТАРНЫМИ БОЛЕЗНЯМИ Учредители: Федеральный научный центр-Всероссийский научно-исследовательский институт экспериментальной ветеринарии им. КИ Скрябина и ЯР Коваленко РАН, (23), 504-509.
- Уббиниязова, Ж. К. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЫ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ЭКОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ БИОЛОГИИ. НАУЧНЫЙ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ «МАТРИЦА НАУЧНОГО ПОЗНАНИЯ», 20.
- Шакарбаев, У. А., Акрамова, Ф. Д., & Азимов, Д. А. (2016). Melanoides kainarensis-новый промежуточный хозяин трематоды Philophthalmus lucipetus (Trematoda, Philophthalmidae). *Российский паразитологический журнал*, (2 (36)), 183-191.
- Sarvinov, E. (2022). THE ESSENCE OF THE DEGREEONY OF SYNONYMS FROM THE STANDPOINT OF THE FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC APPROACH. *Conferencea*, 186-188.
- Nazarovna, X. D., & Uktamovna, E. S. (2023). THE PECULIARITY OF GAMES IN EXPANDING CHILDREN'S THINKING RELAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 620-621.
- Uktamovna, E. S., Nasiba, X., Dilafruz, I., & Saodat, S. (2023). MTT VA OILA BILAN NAMKORLIK. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(5), 400-407.
- Sarvinov U'ktamovna, E. ., & Nozimaxon Shavkat qizi, M. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA IJTIMOIIY-HISSIIY KOMPETENTSIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(5), 1111-1113. извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/2570>
- Intizor, X., Gulhayo, X., & Nafisa, N. . (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ МУАССАЛАРИДА ХАЛҚ ОЎЗАКИ ИЈОДИНИНГ О'РНИ. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(4), 623-625. извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/1446> (Original work published 1 ноябрь 2022 г.)
- Sarvinov, E., Intizor, X., & Gulhayo, X. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМНИНГ USTUVOR VAZIFALARI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(13), 556-561.
- Sarvinov, E. (2022). SYNONIMICAL DEGREEONYMY AS A STYLISTIC PHENOMENON IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE DISCOURSE. *Conferencea*, 189-191.
- Berdiyrov, B. S. (2022). Scientific and Theoretical Basis of Providing Employment of the Population in the Conditions of a Market Economy. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 6321-6325.
- Berdiyrov, B. S. (2022). PROSPECTS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF DIGITAL BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(12), 121-125.
- Berdiyrov, B. S. (2021). USING THE CLUSTER DEVELOPMENT MODEL TOURIST SECTOR. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(12), 13-15.
- Bahodirovna, H. N. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA TARBIYA FANINI O'QITISHNING ASOSIY METOD VA
- VOSITALARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 332-338.
- Bahodirovna, H. N. (2023). Methodological Principles of Teaching The Science of " Education" In Primary Classes. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 366-368.
- Hojiyeva, N. B. (2023). MODERN METHOD IN TEACHING MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS-USING THE CASOGRAPHY METHOD. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 434-439.
- Hojiyeva, N. B. (2023). INCREASING THE INTEREST OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN PRIMARY GRADES. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 430-433.
- Mukumova, D. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF ISMAT BUKHARI FROM THE GAZELS OF SHEIKH KAMALA KHUJANDI. *Scientific Journal of the Fergana State University*, (3), 205. https://doi.org/10.56292/SJFSU/vol_iss3/a205

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Mukumova, D. (2023). ISMAT BUKHARI'S IMPRESSION FROM THE GAZELS OF SHEIKH KAMALA KHUJANDI. *Scientific Journal of the Fergana State University*, (3), 133. https://doi.org/10.56292/SJFSU/vol_iss3/a133
- Мукумова, Д. З. (2020). ISMATI BUKHOROI-FOLLOWER OF THE SHAIKH KAMOL KHUJANDI LITERARY SCHOOL. *Вестник Таджикского национального университета. Серия филологических наук*, (6), 239-243.
- Mukumova, D. Z. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ КАМОЛА ХУДЖАНДИ НА СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ ЖАНРА ГАЗЕЛИ В ПОЭЗИИ XV-XVI ВЕКОВ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПОЭТИЧЕСКОГО КРУГА БУХАРЫ). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (7), 414-419.
- Mukumova, D. Z. (2020). Influence of Kamol Khujandi on the formation of the Genre of the Gazel in the poetry of the XV-XVI centuries (On the example of the poetic circle of Bukhara). *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 07 (87), 414-419.
- Мукумова Дилафруз Зиёдуллаевна (2019). ВЛИЯНИИ ТВОРЧЕСТВА КАМОЛА ХУЖАНДИ НА ТВОРЧЕСТВО БИСОТИ САМАРКАНДИ. *Вестник Педагогического университета*, (4 (81)), 170-175.
- Мукумова, Д. З. (2019). INFLUENCE OF KAMOL KHUJANDI'S CREATIVE WORKS ON BISOT SAMARKANDI'S CREATIVE WORKS. *Вестник Педагогического университета*, (4), 170-175.
- Kurbonalieva, M. S. (2020). THE STRUCTURE AND THE FEATURES OF "TAZKIRAT-USH-SHUARA" MUTRIBI SAMARKANDI. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 581-585.
- Ermatova Mehriniso Bekmurodovna (2022) STEAM TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYASINING MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHDAGI BOLALAR TA'LIMIDAGI AHAMIYATI IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI 2(24) 201-203
- Bekmurodovna, E. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI SHAXSINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TARBIYACHINING ROLI. BOLALARNI XUSHMUOMALALIKKA O'RGATISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(7), 521-523.
- Ermatova Mehriniso Bekmurodovna (2023). STEAM TA'LIM ORQALI BOLALARDA IJODKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке* 1(5) 1219-1221
- Oljabaevna, E. Z. (2022). THE IMPACT OF GADGETS ON CHILDREN'S DEVELOPMENT: DELAYED SPEECH AND AUTISTIC DISORDERS. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 13-16.
- Oljabayevna, Y. Z. (2022). Features of gadget dependence in preschool children. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(10), 15-18.
- Oljabaevna, E. Z. (2022). To Study the Impact of Language and Social Development on Children When Using a Gadget. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 4, 59-61.
- Oljabaevna, E. Z. (2021). DISTINGUISHING SPEECH DEVELOPMENTAL DEFICIENCIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FROM OTHER SPEECH DEFECTS.
- Есназарова, З. (2016). ОСНОВНЫЕ ПОНЯТИЯ И ВИДЫ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ИОНИЗИРУЮЩЕГО ИЗЛУЧЕНИЯ В ЭКОЛОГИИ. *ВЕСТНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА*, 32(3), 33-36.
- Berdiyeva, G. (2022, September). "Fine Art" is A Creative Product for Children in Need of Special Help. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 124-127).
- Nurov, U. I., & Fayziev, C. S. (2023). INTRODUCTION OF THE NEWEST CLINICAL DIAGNOSTIC METHOD FOR THE STUDY OF CONDUCTIVE HEARING LOSS IN PATIENTS. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 2(4), 95-98.
- Нуров, У. И., & Файзиев, С. Ш. (2022). Лечение Больных С Острым Риносинуситом И Обострением Хронического Гнойного Среднего Отита С Помощью Ультразвуковой Кавитации. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 1(12), 113-121.
- Zafar, N., Khasan, B., & Abror, N. (2022). Production of Corrosion Inhibitors Based on Crotonaldehyde and their Inhibitory Properties. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 70, 8.
- Turayev, K. K., Eshkarayev, S. C., Nomozov, A. K., Safarov, A. M., & Abdusalomov, A. R. (2020). Radioekologicheskaya otsenka v sostave pochvy Surkhandar'inskoy oblasti Uzbekistana. *Universum: Khimiya i biologiya: elektron. nauchn. zhurn*, 7, 73.
- Kh, T. K., Ch, E. S., Nomozov, A. K., Safarov, A. M., & Abdusalomov, A. R. (2020). Radioecological assessment in the composition of the soil of the Surkhandarya region of Uzbekistan. *Universum: Chemistry and biology: electron. Scientific. zhurn*, (7), 73.
- Khodjamkulov, S. Z., & Kh, M. Z. (2023). Salsola Oppositifolia acid extract as a green corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel. *Indian Journal of Chemical Technology (IJCT)*, 30(6), 872-877.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Mamazhonov, B., Beknazarov, K., & Nomozov, A. (2023). STUDYING NITROGEN ADSORPTION TO DETERMINE THE POROSITY OF THE SYNTHESIS SORBENT. *American Journal of Engineering, Mechanics and Architecture* (2993-2637), 1(10), 263-268.
- Shaymardanova, M. A., Ch, M. K., Melikulova, G., Khodjamkulov, S. Z., & Nomozov, A. K. (2023). STUDY OF PROCESSE OF OBTAINING MONOPOTASSIUM PHOSPHATE BASED ON MONOSODIUM PHOSPHATE AND POTASSIUM CHLORIDE. *Kimya Problemleri*, 21(3), 279-293.
- Kh S, B., & SZ, K. (2023). Salsola Oppositifolia acid extract as a green corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel.
- Durdubaeva, R., Beknazarov, S., & Nomozov, A. (2022). SYNTHESIS OF 2, 4, 6-TRIETHANOLIMINE-1, 3, 5-TRIAZINE AND ITS APPLICATION AS A CORROSION INHIBITOR OF CARBON STEEL IN 0.5 M H₂SO₄ SOLUTION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 613-618.
- Nomozov, A., Beknazarov, K., & Dzhililov, A. (2022). Synthesis of Corrosion Inhibitor IKPK-1 and its Application for Corrosion Protection of Steel ST20 in 1M HCL. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 10, 23-28.
- Мисиров, З. Х., Бекназаров, Х. С., & Номозов, А. К. У. (2022). ПРИГОТОВЛЕНИЕ ИНГИБИТОРА КОРРОЗИИ НА ОСНОВЕ ОРГАНИЧЕСКИХ И НЕОРГАНИЧЕСКИХ СОЕДИНЕНИЙ И ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЕГО ИНГИБИРУЮЩЕЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ В 1 М РАСТВОРЕ HCL. *Universum: химия и биология*, (11-2 (101)), 34-36.
- Бекназаров, Х. С. (2022). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ЭКСТРАКТА СОЛЯНИКА ОПОЗИТИФОЛИСТНОГО В КАЧЕСТВЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИНГИБИТОРА В СИСТЕМЕ ВОДЯНОГО ОХЛАЖДЕНИЯ. *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS* 3, 27.
- Durdubaeva, R., Beknazarov, S., & Nomozov, A. (2022). СИНТЕЗ 2, 4, 6-ТРИЭТАНОЛИМИН-1, 3, 5-ТРИАЗИНА И ЕГО ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ В КАЧЕСТВЕ ИНГИБИТОРА КОРРОЗИИ УГЛЕРОДИСТОЙ СТАЛИ В 0, 5 М РАСТВОРЕ H₂SO₄. *Science and innovation*, 1(A8), 613-618.
- Nomozov, A. K. U. L., Beknazarov, X. S., & Yo'Ldosheva, S. G. Q. (2022). SALSOLA OPPOSITIFOLIANYING EKSTRAKTINI SUV BILAN SOVUTISH TIZIMIDA SAMARALI INGIBITOR SIFATIDA QO'LLASH TADQIQOTI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(3), 745-752.
- NOMOZOV, A., BEKNAZAROV, K., KHODZHAMKULOV, S., & YULDASHEVA, S. (2022). THE STUDYING OF APPLICATION OF SALSOLA OPPOSITIFOLIA EXTRACT IN 0.5 ML OF SULFURIC ACID AS A GREEN INHIBITOR FOR CORROSION OF CARBON STEEL. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (4), 70-77.
- NOMOZOV, A., BEKNAZAROV, K., KHODZHAMKULOV, S., & YULDASHEVA, S. (2022). THE STUDYING OF APPLICATION OF SALSOLA OPPOSITIFOLIA EXTRACT IN 0.5 ML OF SULFURIC ACID AS A GREEN INHIBITOR FOR CORROSION OF CARBON STEEL. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (4), 70-77.
- NOMOZOV, A. K. U., BEKNAZAROV, K. S., & JALILOV, A. T. (2021). SYNTHESIS OF CORROSION INHIBITORS CONTAINING PHOSPHORUS AND SULFUR BASED ON 2-ETHYLHEXANOL, AND STUDYING ITS PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (10), 239-243.
- Nomzov, A., Qobilova, Z., & Abdusalomov, A. (2019). RESEARCH OF EXTRACTION PHOSPHORIC ACID OBTAINED FROM CENTRAL KZYLKUM IN THE PRESENCE OF ALKALINE METALS. In *ВЫСОКИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ, НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ* (pp. 31-34).
- Ходжамкулов, С. З., Номозов, А. К. У., Меликулова, Г. Э., & Мирзакулов, Х. Ч. (2019). Исследование обесфторивания экстракционной фосфорной кислоты, полученной из термоконцентрата Центральных Кызылкумов в присутствии оксида кремния. *Universum: технические науки*, (2 (59)), 93-96.
- Turayev, K. K. Kh. Kh. Turaev, AS Mukimov, P. Dzh. Tojiyev, MU Karimov.
- Хайруллаевич, С. Н. (2023). Use of Acrobatic Exercises and Their Terms In The Process of Teaching Gymnastics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(9), 80-86.
- Хайруллаевич, С. Н. (2023). AEROBIK GIMNASTIKANING XUSUSIYATLARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 442-448.
- Хайруллаевич, С. Н. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ ДВИЖИТЕЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ВОЗРАСТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ СПОРТИВНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА КАК ИЗ. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 457-464.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

- Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). Norms of gymnasiums and activities of gymnasiums. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 428-434.
- Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). SPORT GIMNASTIKASIDA HARAKATLAR KETMA-KELIGINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 478-491
- Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatlarning ko'chishi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 379-393.
- Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 90-97.
- Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Physical education lessons in the process of umumpedagogik methods. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 345-354.
- Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Jismoniy tarbiya va sport gimnastikaning ahamiyati. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(2), 70-76.
- Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Physical downloads and the rest of fulfilling exercise mutual dependence. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 394-409.

